

Assumption List - STGT study

This section presents the assumption list created by the first author, responsible for coding open coding, after discussing with the second author, an expert in Socio-Technical Grounded Theory.

- LLMs are a gold mine for curious software developers
- LLMs should not be used without supervision
- The biggest advantage of LLMs is facilitate information retrieval
- LLMs are not sentient beings
- Junior developers will still be necessary
- LLMs generate poor-quality code
- Final year Computer Science Students should have real projects where they are allowed to use LLMs
- Educators should make students experience LLM limitations
- LLM tools can be adopted by the majority of companies
- LLMs are just another tool for a software developer